

EMPLOYABILITY IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA FOR 2008-2018 PERIOD

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Employability in the Romanian mountain area represent an economic problem which can be resolved through negentropy. "Negentropy is somehow closely related to the attempt to regulate a system and in other cases, to a deregulation of it...", as demonstrated in the paper "Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis" (Covaci Mihai & Covaci Brîndușa, 2023).

Regarding *persons employed in the population of enterprises established in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 50229.09, 3907.870, 48456.00, 12960.938, 167985902.491, 1.556, .661, 4.357, 1.279, 51147, 31967, 83114, 45747.00, 48456.00, 518.00, 518.00

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .134, .310, -.035, .842, -.035, -.028; R-square .199, .332, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 2439.910, 3560.793, .000, 12960.938, .000, 96.593; MAPS 20,004, 7,321, .000, 29,141, .000, 4,768; MaxAPE 60,720, 23,276, .000, 91,858, .000, 14,455; MAE 1564.214, 2171.830, .000, 7850.298, .000, 57.119; MaxAE 6001,250, 9094,614, .000, 32884,909, .000, 249,467; Normalized BIC 14,858, 2,140, 11,767, 19,157, 11,767, 11,945.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following general picture for I8 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 5.551E-16, 5.551E-16, 12960.938, 15.894; S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3297.208, 29.141; S3-Model_3: .000, .000, 2131,897, 19,595; S4-Model_4: .000, .000, 4403,902, 21,169; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 935.717, 22.375; S6-Model_6: 6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 944.482, 17.354; S7-Model_7: -.035, .298,

637,383, 22,658; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 321.976, 21.466; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 2111,756, 20,304; S10-Model_10: .667, .551, 450,817, 22,334; S11-Model_11: .842, .542, 1082,844, 27,760.

Table 25. Prediction analysis for I8

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229
	UCL	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108
	LCL	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670
	UCL	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017
	LCL	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189
	UCL	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939
	LCL	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385
	UCL	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198
	LCL	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419
	UCL	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504
	LCL	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678
	UCL	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782
	LCL	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573
S7-	Forecast	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286

Model_7:	UCL	3706	4223	4628	4973	5279	5556	5811
	LCL	866	349	-56	-401	-707	-984	-1239
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	863	863	863	863	863	863	863
	UCL	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581
	LCL	146	146	146	146	146	146	146
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619
	UCL	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324
	LCL	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	2481	2629	2778	2926	3075	3223	3372
	UCL	3500	3654	3808	3961	4115	4268	4422
	LCL	1461	1604	1748	1891	2035	2179	2322
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	4950	5303	5656	6009	6362	6715	7068
	UCL	7400	7765	8130	8495	8860	9225	9590
	LCL	2501	2841	3182	3523	3864	4205	4546

Figure 3.16. Graphical forecasting analysis for I8

For *employees in the population of enterprises established in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 33040.09, 1552.505, 32659.00, 5149.078, 26513003.691, .741, .661, .381, 1,279, 17498, 25891, 43389, 29903.00, 32659.00, 35159.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,1,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .181, .361, -4.219E-15, . 920, -4.219E-15, -4.041E-15; R-square .220, .348, -4.219E-15, 1.000, -4.219E-15, -3.952E-15; RMSE 1147.041, 1571.846, .000, 5149.078, .000, 35.520; MAPS 16,181, 8,161, .000, 32,458, .000, 2,731; MaxAPE 44,501, 26,848, .000, 90,313, .000, 6,084; MAE 847,796, 1186,959, .000, 3846,281, .000, 28,507; MaxAE

2394,060, 3293,138, .000, 10348,909, .000, 52,373; Normalized BIC
13.016, 2.576, 9.901, 17.311, 9.901, 9.918.

The resulting forecast statistical models show the following general picture
for I9 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared,
RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 5149.078, 11.656 ;
S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3104.414, 32.458; S3-Model_3:
6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 1900.547, 17.269; S4-Model_4: -1.776E-15, -
1.776E-15, 1561.645, 16.217; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16,
500.767, 17.151; S6-Model_6: .183, .066, 458,583, 14,269; S7-Model_7:
.000, .000, 199,616, 22,287; S8-Model_8: .920, .325, 118.401, 25.365; S9-
Model_9: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 436.269, 9.104; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-
16, .730, 125.901, 14.399; S11-Model_11: .884, .519, 209,268, 13,999.

Table 26. Forecast analysis for I9

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040
	UCL	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513
	LCL	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261
	UCL	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178
	LCL	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600
	UCL	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835

	LCL	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366
S4-	Forecast	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054
Model_4:	UCL	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534
	LCL	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575
S5-	Forecast	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444
Model_5:	UCL	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560
	LCL	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329
S6-	Forecast	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935
Model_6:	UCL	3956	4107	4240	4361	4473	4577	4674
	LCL	1913	1762	1629	1508	1397	1293	1195
S7-	Forecast	784	784	784	784	784	784	784
Model_7:	UCL	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229
	LCL	339	339	339	339	339	339	339
S8-	Forecast	279	255	230	206	181	157	132
Model_8:	UCL	547	523	498	474	449	424	400
	LCL	12	-13	-38	-62	-87	-111	-136
S9-	Forecast	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703
Model_9:	UCL	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676
	LCL	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731
S10-	Forecast	1315	1381	1446	1512	1577	1642	1708
Model_10:	UCL	1600	1784	1940	2081	2214	2340	2461
	LCL	1031	978	953	942	940	945	954
S11-	Forecast	1519	1585	1650	1716	1782	1847	1913
Model_11:	UCL	1993	2061	2129	2196	2264	2332	2400
	LCL	1046	1109	1172	1236	1299	1362	1425

Figure 3.17. Graphical forecasting analysis for I9

Regarding *persons employed in businesses dissolved in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 33040.09, 1552.505, 32659.00, 5149.078, 26513003.691, .741, .661, .381, 1,279, 17498, 25891, 43389, 29903.00, 32659.00, 35159.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,1,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .181, .361, -4.219E-15, . 920, -4.219E-15, -4.041E-15; R-square .220, .348, -4.219E-15, 1.000, -4.219E-15, -3.952E-15; RMSE 1147.041, 1571.846, .000, 5149.078, .000, 35.520; MAPS 16,181, 8,161, .000, 32,458, .000, 2,731; MaxAPE 44,501, 26,848, .000, 90,313, .000, 6,084; MAE 847,796, 1186,959, .000, 3846,281, .000, 28,507; MaxAE

2394,060, 3293,138, .000, 10348,909, .000, 52,373; Normalized BIC
13.016, 2.576, 9.901, 17.311, 9.901, 9.918.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I10 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 5149.078, 11.656 ; S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3104.414, 32.458; S3-Model_3: 6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 1900.547, 17.269; S4-Model_4: -1.776E-15, -1.776E-15, 1561.645, 16.217; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 500.767, 17.151; S6-Model_6: .183, .066, 458,583, 14,269; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 199,616, 22,287; S8-Model_8: .920, .325, 118.401, 25.365; S9-Model_9: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 436.269, 9.104; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, .730, 125.901, 14.399; S11-Model_11: .884, .519, 209,268, 13,999.

Table 27. Prediction analysis for I10

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132
	UCL	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333
	LCL	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	2608	1905	1202	499	-203	-906	-1609
	UCL	8425	7833	7239	6644	6046	5447	4846
	LCL	-3209	-4023	-4835	-5645	-6453	-7259	-8064
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758
	UCL	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738

	LCL	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223
S4-	Forecast	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989
Model_4:	UCL	16293	18905	20908	22597	24086	25431	26668
	LCL	3685	1073	-930	-2620	-4108	-5453	-6690
S5-	Forecast	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961
Model_5:	UCL	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578
	LCL	344	344	344	344	344	344	344
S6-	Forecast	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964
Model_6:	UCL	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344
	LCL	583	583	583	583	583	583	583
S7-	Forecast	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353
Model_7:	UCL	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960
	LCL	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253
S8-	Forecast	608	608	608	608	608	608	608
Model_8:	UCL	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091
	LCL	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
S9-	Forecast	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881
Model_9:	UCL	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678
	LCL	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915
S10-	Forecast	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345
Model_10:	UCL	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854
	LCL	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164
S11-	Forecast	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498
Model_11:	UCL	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901
	LCL	96	96	96	96	96	96	96

Figure 3.18. Graphical forecasting analysis for I10

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For *employees in discontinued businesses in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 5, 50, 75, thus 19691.11, 2969.108, 16786.00, 8907.325, 79340430.111, 1,429, .717, 1.612, 1.400, 26260, 12509, 38769, 13013.50, 16786.00, 25638.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .237, .406, -4.441E-16, .906, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; R-square .175, .307, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 1705.159, 2090.499, .000, 7380.365, .000, 62.468; MAPS 153,926, 136,061, .000, 452,897, .000, 8,589; MaxAPE 965,627, 1010,519, .000, 3513,889, .000, 18,931; MAE 1149,230, 1414,252, .000, 5056,231, .000,

49,200; MaxAE 3380,500, 3815,795, .000, 12668,552, .000, 111,867;

Normalized BIC 14,196, 2,436, 10,921, 18,301, 10,921, 11,039.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I11 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: .886, .399, 7380,365, 28,631; S2-Model_2: .906, .345, 2919,963, 224,322; S3-Model_3: .000, .000, 2674,382, 179,541; S4-Model_4: .814, .356, 2080.164, 58.852; S5-Model_5: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 598.186, 181.602; S6-Model_6: .000, .000, 551,167, 85,338; S7-Model_7: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 279.633, 232.930; S8-Model_8: .000, .000, 208,227, 452,897; S9-Model_9: 3.331E-16, 3.331E-16, 867.027, 34.289; S10-Model_10: .000, .000, 2621,754, 311,506; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 281.036, 57.205.

Table 28. Prediction analysis for I11

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	9513	7449	5384	3320	1256	-809	-2873
	UCL	26965	25229	23486	21738	19985	18227	16464
	LCL	-7939	-	-	-	-	-	-
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	1188	452	-284	-1019	-1755	-2490	-3226
	UCL	8092	7392	6691	5991	5290	4589	3888
	LCL	-5717	-6488	-7259	-8029	-8800	-9570	-
S3-	Forecast	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228

Model_3:	UCL	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395
	LCL	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	2295	1760	1224	689	154	-381	-917
	UCL	7214	6703	6193	5683	5172	4662	4151
	LCL	-2624	-3184	-3745	-4305	-4865	-5425	-5984
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033
	UCL	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413
	LCL	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323
	UCL	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594
	LCL	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	415	415	415	415	415	415	415
	UCL	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060
	LCL	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	289	289	289	289	289	289	289
	UCL	769	769	769	769	769	769	769
	LCL	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314
	UCL	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314
	LCL	315	315	315	315	315	315	315
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200
	UCL	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246
	LCL	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	513	513	513	513	513	513	513
	UCL	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161
	LCL	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135

Figure 3.19. Graphical forecasting analysis for I11

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